

1.0 Introduction

Breathing life into long-forgotten ruins: State Archaeology Dept. is restoring the 13th century Somanathapura temple of the Hoysala period.¹

The newspaper headlines made us recollect the pilot project we undertook for the Department of Archaeology, Museums and Heritage, (DAMH) Government of Karnataka at this site. As practitioner-academics working with geomatics applications^{2,3} in Heritage Conservation-Management (HCM), the article raised two questions. One, on the role of digital and manual data on protected monuments (DPM), that we had recorded as part of the pilot, in the restoration. For the process necessarily involves the coming together of tangible materials and intangible building-crafts knowledge. Two, the sustainable management, including (re)use, of DPM and data on heritage structures (DHS), in ways that can adequately account for: The nuance and individuality of embodied knowledge and non-formulaic approaches to protected monument and heritage structure conservation, typically adopted by craftspeople, and other influencing factors on-ground.

Keeping these questions in mind, our aim in this article is to highlight the central role of skilled craftspeople in HCM on-ground and argue for their intangible knowledge to be included in national-level informatics platforms. While we argue for craftspeople's knowledge we simultaneously argue for the continued relevance of empirical field-based professional knowledge. It plays an important role; in mediating between technology, building-crafts and other influencing factors including bureaucracies, local stakeholders and policy directives, and facilitating cross-sectoral knowledge transfer.

Title: Integrating geomatics and building-crafts knowledge: Adapting FAIR and CARE principles for sustainable and inclusive heritage policy and practice

Our concern in this article is not digital data application towards visualisation, interpretation and user experience (see Kenderdine)⁴ for tourists and the general public, which we discuss elsewhere but for HCM on-ground. We present our arguments by drawing on the Panchalingeshwara (PL) project and supplement our analyses with observations from other projects we worked on as professionals, nationally and internationally (Section 3.0). Although commenced over five years ago the PL project is incomplete. Opportunities for field-based professionals, working with protected monuments, to see entire project cycles are uncommon because of the scale and magnitude of such works, frequent changes in administrative bureaucracies and budget allocations. Among other roles in HCM, our team undertakes consultancy on data capture before, during, and after structural conservation, including reconstruction, restoration and repair of monuments and heritage structures. We use these terms in their technical capacity: Reconstruction as reusing existing and new material in rebuilding, restoration as reusing existing and new material in rebuilding without any speculation, and repair as using only existing material.

Extending our analyses of HCM on-ground we make a case for policy-level applications of our suggestions by national-level data informatics platforms such as Open Government Data⁵ and Bhuvan.⁶ Over time, Bhuvan, a geo-portal, initially designed to share topographic data on natural and human-made resources, began to host national-level DPM⁷ as well. Now it is a resource data mapping, sharing and management platform that enables sustainable and inclusive planning and decision-making, by various government departments. We shortly anticipate such platforms hosting DHS as well and suggest a need to include not just tangible data but also intangible knowledge on the nation's monuments and heritage. By intangible we do

Title: Integrating geomatics and building-crafts knowledge: Adapting FAIR and CARE principles for sustainable and inclusive heritage policy and practice

not mean just customs, folk performances and traditional knowledge systems but also knowledge of traditional building materials and construction techniques central to HCM on-ground. A number of heritage-based projects of the Department of Science and Technology (DST), including, SHRI and IHDSR,⁸ and national schemes for the empowerment of artisans and craftspeople (the Prime Minister's Vishwakarma Yojana)⁹ include the former. Few discuss a need to record the latter, sustainably and inclusively.

In foregrounding the need, we also draw on specific project experiences including the DST's India Digital Heritage initiative^{10,11} under which we recorded living crafts of Hampi, a UNESCO World Heritage Site (WHS), over three years, and the 3d-web-based 'day-to-day' heritage management platform (HIMP) we developed for the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI).¹² Considering HCM at the national-level, the India INTACH Charter for the Conservation of Unprotected Architectural Heritage and Sites in India notes two broad approaches to HCM practice: one largely applied to the nation's vast unprotected heritage structures, and the other typically adopted for its limited number of legally recognised monuments.¹³ Given the sheer number and diversity of the former, which continue to survive and remain in use, the charter argues for the central role of *Sthapathis/Sompuras/Rajmistris* (building craftspeople) as 'unique living resources' in caring for heritage structures and monuments. For example, Karnataka state recognises 848 monuments under the Karnataka Ancient Monuments and Scheduled Remains Act of 1961, which are managed by DAMH and 609 monuments under the Ancient Monuments and Scheduled Remains Act, modified 2010, managed by the ASI.¹⁴ Whereas just the city of Bangalore lists at least 800¹⁵ heritage structures (not legally recognised). As heritage data increasingly integrates with digital technologies the gap in informatics on tangible DHS is

currently being addressed piecemeal by diverse agencies. However, not much attention is being given to the holders of intangible knowledge. We argue that it is vital to address this gap for collective benefit

In Section 2.0 we summarise the PL pilot project, evaluate digital and manual technologies of data capture, and connect our analyses to building-crafts and HCM on-ground including influencing factors. Initially, DAMH visualised the project as a straightforward exercise in monument-recording using digital technologies. However, through dialogue we suggested reframing the project as a programme to develop applicable standards for all their monuments. Currently, DAMH holds 3d-laser scanning data on 432 monuments.¹⁶ Given the increasingly voluminous and diverse digital data being held by such agencies, the questions we raised with the agency in 2016, on data sustainability and reuse, become relevant again. In Section 3.0 we touch on these questions and discuss three key points, on quantity, quality and (re)usability of data, including dissemination.

During the pilot project, documenting for restoration did not arise as the project intent was to just capture DPM. As digital humanities streams widen their ambit, we increasingly observe efforts to capture intangible knowledge held by craftspeople.^{17,18} Hence, in Section 4.0 we discuss the way forward towards an integrated approach that would account for not just data sustainability but also inclusivity of such stakeholder knowledge. While a vital research question for the future remains, what fresh social and technological challenges will such commingling raise, we suggest an immediate way forward. Namely, *adapting* the CARE and FAIR principles in ways that are relevant to our specific socio-cultural and geographical context for both national-level geoportals such as BHUVAN and HCM policies.

2.0 The pilot project, building-crafts and supplementary field-based observations

The DAMH approached us (among other experts), in 2015-16, to develop a digital database of few monuments. We offered to undertake 2D-mapping, using Computer Aided Design (CAD) and photo documentation, primarily for record and monument conservation planning (including condition assessment and works prioritisation) for one of their divisions. We also suggested hosting the data on our HIMP platform.¹² However, as we continued to discuss the agency's requirements, we realised their interest was record but the approach, with multiple teams digitising monuments of different divisions, would be piecemeal and DAMH would have minimal control over the output. As practitioner-academics with over 15 years of individual field-experience, we had often observed the failure of successive projects to build on DPM and DHS gathered through previous projects. The reasons are varied and range from ongoing issues of software (in)compatibility, scale of architectural drawings, depth of construction details, missing information on the monument and adoption of digital technologies in an arbitrary manner. Typically, individual projects stored data (online and offline) as catalogues thereby replicating information, unsustainably.

We offered a more viable approach, undertaking a pilot project, to evaluate both manual and digital data capture methods by assessing accessibility, cost, materials, and manpower and enabling DAMH to develop a standardised technical terms of reference document, to capture diverse monument data. DAMH accepted our suggestion and we mutually agreed to limit the methods to manual recording and laser scanning, excluding photogrammetry and remote sensing (RS). We believed photogrammetry would be more useful for structural conservation and obtaining RS

imagery was an expensive and time-consuming proposition for the agency, in 2016. Recent advancements have made photogrammetry more intuitive enabling semi-skilled teams to adopt the technique in the field using smartphones.^{19,20}

We chose the PL site in consultation with DAMH engineers. We deemed the structure, including scale, size and detailing, as representative of the monument typology protected by the agency. Additionally, its location, in terms of ease of access and its condition, partly missing portions and partly covered with vegetation, made it suitable to evaluate manual and digital recording (Figure 1). Moreover, the structure was not under worship, enabling unrestricted access to all parts. The site encompasses a Hoysala-period (13th century CE) temple with five sanctum-sanctorum, built with composite stone masonry, occupying 550 sqm plinth area. It is located close to the Keshava Temple, a nationally-protected monument and UNESCO WHS.

2.1 Evaluating data capture methodologies

Our team had adopted digital technologies in data capture at other sites but the PL pilot was the first project where we systematically compared both methods at the same site. For the project we defined manual recording as physically measuring the structure with tapes and/or digital devices, and transcribing the measurements on paper/computer (Figure 2). And laser scanning as collecting '3D coordinates of a given region of an object's surface automatically and in a systematic pattern at a high rate achieving the results in near real time.'²¹

The phrase 'near real time' indicates a key difference between both: The scanner does not distinguish between objects and surfaces and registers everything as data.

Whereas manual methods offer flexibility in determining what and how much detail to capture depending on the professional's field-based knowledge.

Given the seeming ease of operation, one might be tempted to assume that digital recording does not require detailed planning, including site preparation. However, site planning and technical skills, including thorough knowledge of the equipment and site conditions, their limitations and capabilities, is both vital and necessary to obtain the most efficient capture of data through digital recording.²² Our experiences on the PL project and at other sites corroborate a need for professionals with field-knowledge to negotiate site conditions and influencing factors, whether from heritage or geomatics.

Based on years of experience in manual data capture, we estimated that a senior architect specialised in historical structure documentation and two junior architects would suffice to develop base (architectural) drawings such as plans, elevations, sections and cross sections. Our calculations proved true. For digital recording, in consultation with the vendor we determined that one technically-qualified person and one assistant would suffice. Considering time and cost implications of both methods we observed that manual recording required four times more time on-site compared to digital recording. Whereas both required similar time off-site. Digital recording however was at least four times more expensive than manual recording.

Site conditions, including visibility and accessibility, were common concerns for manual and digital recording (and restoration, Section 2.2). When we commenced the pilot in 2017, thick vegetation partially obscured the site, causing concerns over masonry collapse and faunal presence. While the manual recording team easily navigated the uneven terrain to access the site, the digital team and hired labourers had to carefully manoeuvre expensive equipment and scaffolding over it. Scaffolding

proved necessary as there was no suitable tree or structure nearby to mount equipment and obtain higher-elevation scans (Figure 3a).²³ Another common concern was the role of local stakeholders and heritage enthusiasts. On hearing about the project, a volunteer group cleared surrounding vegetation, before our arrival, as *shramdaan*. While appreciating the effort we discussed a need to undertake such works scientifically without risk to either themselves or the monument. Such incidents are common and highlight the range of influencing factors on-ground (Section 2.2, stakeholder influence and 4.0, CARE principles).

During data capture and processing, the digital team more-or-less followed standard procedure: Scanning the structure, registering the data against reference markers (orbs) erected on-site (Figure 3a), exporting this data onto computers as 'point-cloud' (pts format) (Figure 3b), processing the point-cloud, aligning it with the orbs, and generating 3D-mesh output. Unlike manual recording, the site had to be undisturbed during scanning: Orbs had to remain fixed for accurate processing, (curious) onlookers and animal movement impacted clean capture of data, tree cover and shadow were digital distractions. Whereas with manual recording vegetation provides welcome shade and drawings can be generated on-site irrespective of onlookers, allowing one to immediately check for omissions.

However, laser scan data can find varied future use: For 3d-prints of details (Figure 3c), creating walkthroughs, and generating detailed 2D-drawings. In our case the latter outputs proved rudimentary (Figure 3d) without additional costs. Attempting to create a virtual walkthrough we realised that users required specific software (in our case FARO Scene) to view the rendering and other software was needed to maintain access to point-cloud data. The process was neither one-click nor seamless.

Following the outcome, we recommended that digital and manual methods were complementary; one could not replace the other. Their usage depended on need, time and budget.^{24,25} Manual recording enabled us to comprehend the site as a complex and not isolated structure and RS-GIS helped corroborate field observations. Scholars have built on historical records²⁶ and RS imagery²⁷ to suggest that the complex was likely located at the north-east corner of fortifications that once enclosed Somanathapura.

While the PL project represented data-capture for record documentation is equally important during and after structural conservation. Data capture for record only collects visible information. One comprehends the 3d-nuances of masonry, through reverse engineering, during structural conservation. Such learning on-ground, though uncommon (Section 1.0), is crucial given the site-specific variations in traditional building materials and construction techniques. Experienced building craftspeople hold such valuable empirical knowledge through a combination of embodied cognition (knowing through action), haptic (knowing through touch) and tacit knowledge (knowing through experience) (Figure 4). We observed heritage agencies' reliance on craftspeople to skillfully restore missing portions of a 1000-year-old monument in north Karnataka. They reused existing stone blocks to provide structural stability and control project cost and time. Monumental stone masonry is equivalent to a three-dimensional jigsaw; blocks cannot be re-inserted ad-hoc. Effectively PL structural conservation would require skilled craftspeople with field-based knowledge of the architectural style, construction technology, and material (load bearing, dry composite granite block masonry supporting box action).

2.2 Building-crafts as knowledge not 'know-how'

Referring to the headlines in the introduction we revisited the PL site in 2023-24, anticipating work completion. We also discussed the project with the building-crafts team and understood that it was decided to reconstruct most of the structure, restore some internal elements and repair some parts and not just stabilise the ruins. Broadly the team followed a standard procedure for structural conservation: Numbering existing stone masonry, dismantling, stacking on-site and re-using existing stones. Similar to when we commenced documentation in 2017, the crafts team also raised concerns over site conditions (visibility) and influencing factors (see below). Before commencing works it was important for the team to expose the structure's base-course (not to be confused with foundation courses below or plinth courses above) to determine the temple outline.

As practitioners we may not favour the outcome of reconstruction at PL, for example, the stone screens. Simultaneously though, we cannot deny the embodied knowledge of the architectural style, construction technology, and traditional materials, held by the team. Such knowledge led them to design the screens based on over 20 years of hands-on experience in Hoysala temple (re)construction. Similarly, we may not favour the use of incompatible mortar and wall infill. However, we cannot deny the time and cost implications and client demands that usually lead such teams to adopt contemporary materials and techniques in structural conservation. One sculptor asserted that craftspeople with skill in historic mortar were readily available but such teams were no longer part of reconstruction projects. He added that usually local stakeholders demanded that heritage structures look 'new' and 'finished'. They did not appreciate craftspeople using existing, deteriorated-in-appearance but structurally sound stones. Similarly, public works engineers preferred size-stone

masonry foundation to the existing well-compacted base with boulders and soil infill, which the crafts team reiterates has ably supported such monuments for centuries. We have similarly observed the role of stakeholders in other sites, not just those protected by the DAMH or the ASI, in shaping HCM on-ground.

However, in this article, through the above discussion, the question we open to further debate is, can digital technologies efficiently and effectively account for the individuality of embodied knowledge and non-formulaic approaches to monument (re)construction typically adopted by building craftspeople? At what point does the capture of such nuances of HCM on-ground, such as, knowing through action, touch, and experience, and the variations due to site-constraints, become unsustainable. We have touched on influencing factors above and now discuss knowing.

In Jan 2024, the PL craft team's supervisor was working on a DAMH monument near Hampi WHS; a temple reconstruction project. He noted that they work with large blocks delivered to site and are not part of the team that selects the quarry or the stone and demonstrated the techniques they adopt to determine stone composition and characteristics. He judged the (stone) grain by touch and gauged its suitability for sculpting as beam, column, or wall by tapping the block with a chisel to determine the loading direction (Figure 4). As conservation professionals we typically learn about the density of stone grains and bedding direction in the classroom or craftspeople like him and sometimes through lab tests to determine grade. Such instances are many. Here we are not cataloguing the various forms of knowing but building on Timothy Ingold's long-standing work – at the intersection of archaeology, architecture, art and anthropology, to examine the relationship between material objects and their social contexts – arguing for their inclusion as knowledge and not just 'knowhow'.^{28,29} Such knowledge is as significant as a field-based professional's

Title: Integrating geomatics and building-crafts knowledge: Adapting FAIR and CARE principles for sustainable and inclusive heritage policy and practice

knowledge (of site conditions, negotiating influencing factors, nuances of manual recording) and not merely useful skills to be used ad-hoc. Both are gained through 'doing by hand' in a sustained manner and not by 'formulaic' handing down of seemingly 'unchanged' tradition.^{28,29}

As attempts to digitise such knowledge^{17,18} become widespread, the focus should be, how can digitisation *aid* building craftspeople, who are an integral part of HCM on-ground. One could incorporate collaborative questions into projects, whether research or practice-based, to understand their needs and wants. Do they desire their processes to be digitised? Can digitisation serve their day-to-day practice, for example, to ease the process of knowledge-transfer through remote collaboration (of significance in a post-covid world).³⁰ Even as heritage agencies, such as the ASI, widely adopt digital technologies for recording, they note a gap that has risen due to the limited availability of skilled building craftspeople and wider need for such skills in structural conservation.³¹

While the results of the pilot were meant to inform policy-level decisions for one agency, the widespread and diverse adoption of digital technologies and knowledge gap, similarities of issues across sites, leads us to think about sustainable and inclusive futures for heritage informatics at a national level.

3.0 From HCM on-ground to national-level heritage informatics

In the seven years since the PL project, need for multidisciplinary skills are widely recognised in HCM policy and practice. We similarly observe a parallel move, from a piecemeal to integrated approach to heritage informatics, in the field of geomatics. Courses and degrees now offer training in digital humanities, computational archaeology, spatial analytics, and machine learning for archaeology. The social and

technological challenges raised by such blending will remain ongoing research questions. In the immediate future, what might the way forward be?

We suggest elaborating the research questions (Section 1.0) at policy-level: on integrating tangible material record with intangible knowledge in heritage informatics and managing such data sustainably and inclusively, while accounting for on-ground realities. We set-out entry-level questions on inclusivity in Section 2.2 and now elaborate sustainability through the parameters of quantity, quality and (re)usability based on questions we raised with DAMH in 2016 and other heritage agencies and projects across India. Our recent individual engagements with heritage informatics include evaluating India-UK funded heritage and digital technologies projects, since 2015 and an international archaeological data management project.³²

First, the quantity of data collected and generated digitally. Where would agencies store the recorded data of all their sites? Would they host their own servers? Who, i.e., which organisational levels would access the data? Do they visualise some of the data being open source and others under filters? What uses do they anticipate for the data? Would they be able to use the data as is? What challenges might they face related to software and hardware compatibility? For example, the product might typically be licensed to only one individual but how many such individuals would they procure licences for? What would the recurring costs of licences be? Typically, both softwares and hardwares come with built-in expiry due to rapid advancements in the sector and multiple softwares and licences are needed to access the data. Reflecting on such questions from a data sustainability perspective led us to conclude that more data does not necessarily result in more usable data.

Second, the quality of output, by which we mean data resolution, whether raster or vector. We observe that high-resolution formats and large-scale outputs are not

always useful or necessary. Sometimes coarser resolution and smaller-scale outputs are all that is needed. The key question in deciding quality, we suggest, is the purpose for which the data is being collected, for record, structural conservation, site interpretation and so on. We conclude that a data management plan should be part of the site conservation-management plan. Rather than uncritically collecting all data on the protected monument or heritage structure, this plan would unambiguously state the purpose of data collection.

Third, the effective and efficient re-usability of digital data across different levels of expertise, within the agency and associated stakeholders. This last aspect is of some importance as the heritage field is necessarily multidisciplinary, requiring perspectives from geomatics, HCM and building-crafts. Even if the expert has general domain expertise s/he won't necessarily have field-based knowledge across other domains. Moreover, as technologies advance constantly, the geomatics and HCM experts and, as we anticipate going forward, building craftspeople will need to dedicate time and resources on an ongoing basis to upgrade their skills, equipment and software applications. This is a real challenge. Simultaneously, we acknowledge that technology is also becoming more intuitive, permitting semi-skilled and unskilled personnel to capture heritage data.¹⁹ Having established that HCM on-ground is highly iterative, we suggest human knowledge remains key to account for the variability of each structure, site, and context.

While individual disciplines are addressing the above questions to aid informed decision-making and improve project efficacy, more effort is needed to integrate them. For example, considering recording and documentation, researchers are attempting to build open-source digital libraries of socio-culturally specific historical architectural models and details using Building Information Modelling (BIM)

Title: Integrating geomatics and building-crafts knowledge: Adapting FAIR and CARE principles for sustainable and inclusive heritage policy and practice

software³³ and open-source digital platforms for cultural heritage applications (See Arches³⁴). Ideally, such projects can be taken up across geographies.³⁵ In determining a methodology to apply spatial data to national-level development schemes, in a way that is both sustainable and inclusive, Gupta et. al (2023:126)³⁶ argue that although a 'data deluge' may appear beneficial and attractive, its usability is 'not straightforward' and comes with many challenges. Their argument was made in the context of how data might benefit marginalised castes and gender. Considering HCM on-ground, we suggest the marginalised group would be building craftspeople.

Having elaborated long-term policy-level questions for wider debate through cross-disciplinary engagement, we present an immediate way forward for consideration in the next section, adapting the CARE and FAIR principles, in a contextually-relevant manner for national-level heritage informatics management, such as BHUVAN.

4.0 Way forward

Reiterating our interest in cross-disciplinary engagement in policy and practice, we call on recent scholarship from data sciences, including archaeology,³⁷ we suggest incorporating the FAIR and CARE principles to realise our objective of sustainable and inclusive data management in the short-term. FAIR, an acronym for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable, was first proposed by a consortium of scholars and industry³⁸ keeping in mind a need to 'enhance³⁸ the reusability' of data sets with emphasis on 'enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use the data'. The guiding vision in developing FAIR was that 'good data management is not a goal in itself' but a conduit to furthering knowledge and innovation. The consortium was particularly concerned with putting in place 'long-term care' strategies for publicly-funded digital data sets. An acronym for Collective Benefit, Authority to

Title: Integrating geomatics and building-crafts knowledge: Adapting FAIR and CARE principles for sustainable and inclusive heritage policy and practice

Control, Responsibility, and Ethics, the CARE principles were proposed by the International Indigenous Data Sovereignty Interest Group³⁹ in light of the widespread use of data as a resource towards commercialisation. Here the goal was to mitigate exploitation of vulnerable peoples' data. Given its focus on 'people and purpose' CARE complements FAIR and one cannot mention one without the other. Although it might appear a bit simplistic, a useful way to understand their contextual application in HCM informatics would be to see FAIR as focused on sustainable data management and CARE on the responsible and inclusive collection, use, and dissemination of data.

The three parameters of data that we discussed in section 3.0 relate directly to the FAIR principles. Whereas the four main principles expressed by CARE co-relate with HCM on-ground, given the range of stakeholders and influencing factors, both direct and indirect. For instance, we did not wholly agree with the process and nature of reconstruction adopted at the PL site as the approach was not in complete agreement with either their embodied knowledge systems or the historical construction systems of protected monuments and heritage structures. However, in keeping with the ethos of the India INTACH Charter we favour reconstruction over preservation as-is and the central role of building craftspeople in the process. In keeping with the realities of HCM in India, we cannot deny stakeholder interest in seeking to have monuments and structures brought back to larger public consciousness. Given the shift to integrate heritage data on national-level portals we believe in the not-too-distant future BHUVAN could host not just tangible but intangible HCM data as well. And as we have established one form of data cannot replace the other, all have key roles to play. Hence the need to not only bring together CARE and FAIR principles but also adapt them as appropriate to our

Title: Integrating geomatics and building-crafts knowledge: Adapting FAIR and CARE principles for sustainable and inclusive heritage policy and practice

geographical and socio-cultural context. Adopting these principles uncritically would defeat not just the aims of both data management principles but also the aims of HCM practice and policy, namely to be contextual, sustainable, inclusive and offer collective benefit.

5.0 Acknowledgments

We undertook the pilot project under the aegis of the Centre for Heritage Initiatives (CHI), a collaboration between Saythu...Linking People and Heritage and Dayananda Sagar College of Architecture. Our thanks to the Principal, Dr Rama Subramanian, Mr Pankaj Modi, Co-Director, CHI and the digital recording team, Nebula Technologies, led by Mr B.Gururaj and Mr Naveen Raju. Thanks also to the Commissioner, Ms N. Manjula, Mr Doreraju, Archaeological Conservation Engineer, DAMH and various building-crafts teams for sharing their knowledge. A special mention to Mr S. Acharya, Karkala.

Figure 1: PL site in context

- a. Site plan overlay on Google Earth (GE) imagery (©2024 Airbus). Settlement extent as identified by Settar (2011).²⁵
- b. Vegetation-covered monument, GE imagery (©2016 Maxar Technologies) overlay by authors indicating current profile of the temple.
- c. The restored monument on GE imagery (©2024 Airbus).
- d. Field photograph (from SW) during manual recording. 2017. Source: The authors.
- e. Field photograph (from SE). 2023. Source: The authors.

Title: Integrating geomatics and building-crafts knowledge: Adapting FAIR and CARE principles for sustainable and inclusive heritage policy and practice

Figure 2: Various stages of manual recording and its output, PL complex, 2017.

Source: Project team.

- a. Field sketch indicating process of recording a cross-section and architectural details.
- b. Observing and sketching construction and architectural details of the shikara (team-member on partially-collapsed mantapa roof).
- c. East elevation of the monument (showing conjectural outline of the missing portions).
- d. Plan of the monument (showing conjectural outline of the missing portions).

Figure 3: Various stages of digital recording and its output, PL complex, 2017.
Source: Project team.

- a. Digital recording process with white orb in the foreground and scaffolding in the background. Image digitally cleaned in Photoshop to eliminate moving subjects (visual distraction that obscures details). West view.
- b. Point cloud rendered output. Notice the scaffolding in all four corners. View from south-east.
- c. Rudimentary 2D drawing output of one sanctum from the point-cloud data.
- d. Sample 3D output of one pillar, generated as a mesh infill and rendered over point-cloud data - intended to be used as a pillar prototype in the 3d-walkthrough.

Figure 4: Building craftspeople and forms of knowing. Source: The authors.

- a. Knowing through experience: Senior craftsperson's sketch of stone courses and numbering technique alongside elevation drawings by documentation team, recorded manually.
- b. Knowing through action: Stone-cutters at the quarry, selecting suitable portions of the bedrock and determining appropriate locations and number of wedges required to split the block from the rock-face.
- c. Knowing through touch: Crafts team examining the suitability of a quarried-stone block on-site, to determine its load-bearing capacity and finished dimensions.

¹Kumar R.K., Breathing life into long-forgotten ruins. *The Hindu*, Karnataka edition, 2019, October 29. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/karnataka/breathing-life-into-long-forgotten-ruins/article29826331.ece>

²Gomasasca (2009) discusses diverse geo-spatial data capturing technologies that fall under the geomatics umbrella, in detail.

³Gomasasca, M. A., *Basics of Geomatics*, Springer, London, New York, 2009.

⁴<https://www.thehindu.com/news/cities/bangalore/the-digital-has-a-big-role-to-play-in-the-decolonisation-of-museums/article67795475.ece> (accessed 26 February 2024).

⁵<https://data.gov.in/> (accessed 27 January 2023).

⁶<https://bhuvan.nrsc.gov.in/home/index.php> (accessed 27 January 2023).

⁷Navalgund, R. and Korisettar, R., Preface: Geospatial techniques in archaeology. *Current Science*, 2017. 113(10), 1858–1858. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26494836>.

⁸<https://dst.gov.in/science-and-heritage-research-initiative-shri>;
<https://dst.gov.in/indian-heritage-digital-space-research> (accessed 15 February 2024).

⁹<https://www.india.gov.in/spotlight/pradhan-mantri-vishwakarma-scheme> (accessed 15 February 2024).

¹⁰Rajangam K., Rangachar V. and Prasad A, *Living crafts of the Hampi region: A research report of the Crafts Council of Karnataka's India Digital Heritage Project- The extensive survey, digital archiving, documentation and crafts-centric end-user experience of crafts in and around Hampi*. Bangalore, Crafts Council of Karnataka. 2016.

¹¹Rajangam K., Best laid plans: Research design and the field in a study of crafts in the Hampi region, *Craft Research*, 2017, 8(1), 9-31.

¹²Rajangam K. and Modi P, Heritage Information Management Package (HIMP) – technology and experience driven approach towards efficiently managing India's built heritage sites. In Proceedings of Built Heritage 2013-Monitoring Conservation Management, Nov 18-20, Milan, Politecnico Di Milano, 2013.

¹³INTACH, INTACH Charter: Principles, 2016. <http://www.intach.org/about-charter-principles.php> (accessed 06 Feb 2024).

¹⁴<https://archaeology.karnataka.gov.in/page/Monuments/Ancient+Monuments/en> (accessed 27 January 2024).

¹⁵<https://www.intachblr.org/other.html> (accessed 27 January 2024).

¹⁶<https://archaeology.karnataka.gov.in/page/Monuments/State+Protected+Heritage+monuments+3D+Laser+Scanning+-+Bengaluru+Division/en> (accessed 27 January 2024).

<https://archaeology.karnataka.gov.in/page/Monuments/State+Protected+Monuments+-+3D+Laser+Scanning+-+Mysuru+Division/en> (accessed 27 January 2024).

<https://archaeology.karnataka.gov.in/page/Monuments/State+Protected+Monuments+-+3D+Laser+Scanning+-+Kalaburgi+Division/en> (accessed 27 January 2024).

¹⁷Zabulis, X et. al, Digitisation of Traditional Craft Processes. *J. Comput. Cult. Herit*, 2022, 15(3), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3494675>.

¹⁸Chatterjee, A., Alvelos, H., Hands Versus Fingers: Leveraging Digital Technology Towards Sustaining Traditional Crafts and Industrial Practices. In Perspectives on Design and Digital Communication (eds. Martins, N., Brandão, D. and Raposo, D.), Springer Series in Design and Innovation, 8, Cham, Springer, 2021. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49647-0_13.

¹⁹Recently, we utilised a photogrammetry software capable of easily stitching photographs together (see Harshavardhan (2022) for method). Working with undergraduate students of architecture we recorded a small shrine.

²⁰Harshavardhan, M., Spatial Analysis and 3d Mapping Historic Landscapes: Implications of Adopting an Integrated Approach in Simulation and Visualization of Landscapes. In *Proceedings of the Satellite Workshops of ICVGIP 2021*. (ed. Mudenagudi, U., Nigam, A., Sarvadevabhatla, R.K. and Choudhary, A.), Springer, Singapore, 2022. 924. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-4136-8_7.

²¹Böhler, W. and Marbs, A., 3D Scanning Instruments. In Proceedings of CIPA WG6 Scanning for Cultural Heritage Recording, September 1–2, Corfu, Greece, 2002.

²²Thomson, C. 3 types of terrestrial laser scanners. Correvate Ltd. 2021. (Accessed 12 Dec 2023). <https://info.vercator.com/blog/3-types-of-terrestrial-laser-scanners>.

²³Today drone-mounted lasers have largely eliminated the need for scaffolding but expertise remains necessary. Not all drone operators are skilled at heritage documentation. Additionally, No Objection Certificates are mandatory to fly drones.

²⁴See Historic England handbook's graph (2018:2) comparing different recording techniques ranging from manual to diverse digital methods, relative to object size and complexity.

²⁵Historic England, 3D Laser Scanning for Heritage: Advice and Guidance on the Use of Laser Scanning in Archaeology and Architecture. Swindon, Historic England, 2018.

²⁶Devaraj, D. V., History of Somanathapura Temple-Complex in Socio-Economic and Cultural Perspectives. Mysore, Directorate of Archaeology & Museums in Karnataka, 1994.

²⁷Settar, S., Somanathapura: An illustrated monograph. Bangalore, 2nd ed. Ruvari, Abhinava Imprint, 2011.

²⁸Ingold, T., *Knowing from the inside: Cross-disciplinary experiments with matters of pedagogy*. (ed.), London, Bloomsbury Academic, 2022.

²⁹Ingold, T., *The Perception of the Environment: Essays on livelihood, dwelling and skill*. London and NY, Routledge, 2000.

³⁰Panneels, I., Helgason, I., Smyth, M., Darzentas, D., Hocking, L., & Shillito, A., Distance: digital immersive technologies and craft engagement. In Connectivity and Creativity in Times of Conflict, Cumulus Conference Proceedings, Antwerp, 2023.

³¹Ramesh S and DHNS, ASI has embraced tech to document, determine status of monuments. *Deccan Herald*, Bangalore edition. 2023, February 04. <https://www.deccanherald.com/india/karnataka/bengaluru/asi-has-embraced-tech-to-document-determine-status-of-monuments-1187999.html>.

³²Tracing the digital thread: <https://qtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=AH%2FX00001X%2F1>; Mapping Archaeological Heritage in South Asia: <https://www.mahsa.arch.cam.ac.uk/>

³³Aburamadan R, Trillo C, Cotella VA, Di Perna E, Ncube C, Moustaka A, Udeaja C, Awuah K G B., Developing a heritage BIM shared library for two case studies in Jordan's heritage: The House of Art in Amman and the Qaqish House in the World Heritage City of As-Salt, *Herit Sci*, 2022, 10(1), 196. doi:10.1186/s40494-022-00836-w.

³⁴<https://www.archesproject.org/> (accessed 15 February 2024).

³⁵Agarwal S., Tiwari S P., Pande H., Ragahavendran S., Grover C., Semwal E. and Srivastava S., *Exploring footprints of the past, heritage documentation: A geospatial approach*, IIRS, ISRO, DoS, Government of India, Dehradun, 2022.

³⁶Gupta, S., Reddy, A., Reddy, S.C., Sakaram A. and Ravisankar T., Spatial data analysis of Mahatma Gandhi national rural employment guarantee scheme and its influencing factors. *Spat. Inf. Res.*, 2023, 31, 125–133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41324-022-00475-0>.

³⁷Gupta, N., Bonneau, N. and Elvidge, M., Connecting Past to Present: Enacting Indigenous Data Governance Principles in Westbank First Nation's Archaeology and Digital Heritage. *Arch.* 2022, 18, 623–650. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11759-022-09466-x>.

³⁸Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg IJ, Appleton G, Axton M, Baak A, Blomberg N, Boiten JW, da Silva Santos LB, Bourne PE, Bouwman J, Brookes AJ, Clark T, Crosas M, Dillo I, Dumon O, Edmunds S, Evelo CT, Finkers R, Gonzalez-Beltran A, Gray AJ, Groth P, Goble C, Grethe JS, Heringa J, 't Hoen PA, Hooft R, Kuhn T, Kok R, Kok J, Lusher SJ, Martone ME, Mons A, Packer AL, Persson B, Rocca-Serra P, Roos M, van Schaik R, Sansone SA, Schultes E, Sengstag T, Slater T, Strawn G, Swertz MA, Thompson M, van der Lei J, van Mulligen E, Velterop J, Waagmeester A, Wittenburg P, Wolstencroft K, Zhao J and Mons B, The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data.*, 2016, Mar 15(3), 1600-18. doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.

³⁹Carroll, S.R., Garba, I., Figueroa-Rodriguez, O.L., Holbrook, J., Lovett, R., Materechera, S., Parsons, M., Raseroka, K., Rodriguez-Lonebear, D., Rowe, R., Sara, R., Walker, J.D., Anderson, J. and Hudson, M., The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance. *Data Science Journal*, 2020, 19(1), 43. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043>.